

ISSN 2181-2357

XALQARO NAZARIY VA AMALIY TADQIQOTLAR
JURNALI

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL RESEARCH

JURNAL FARG'ONA POLITEXNIKA
INSTITUTI HAMKORLIGIDA NASHR
ETILADI

VOLUME 3,
Issue 2
2023

«Al-Ferganus» MChJ.

A. M. Abdullayev

«Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali»

Ilmiy jurnal.

2021 yil noyabrdan beri nashr etilmoqda.

Oyiga bir marta nashr etiladi. 16+

3-tom, 2 -son.

Fevral 2023 y.

Tahririyat kengashi raisi Salomov O'ktam Raximovich, FarPI rektori

Bosh muharrir K. I. Kurpayanidi

Tahririyat hay'ati: A.M.Abdullaev, M.S.Ashurov, E.A.Mo'minova, K.X.Abduraxmonov, A.N.Asaul, A.V.Burkov, U.V.G'ofurov, M.A.Ikromov, D.Kudbiev, E.S.Margianiti, B.Obrenovich, L.NA Sultonov, L.NA. , A.Xasanov, Sh.T.Karimov, Sh.Sh.Salixanova, U.K.Alimov, S.M.Turabdjano, B.A.Alimatov, R.J.Tozhiyev, A.A.Risqulov, B.M.Tursunov, S. F. Ergashev, J.D.Axmedov, Kh.A. Akramov, M.X. Xakimov, Sh.M. Iskandarova, Z.M. Sobirova, A.M. Muxtarova, L.M. Babakhodjaeva..

Tahririyat manzili: 150107

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uy

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E-mail: alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

IF(Impact Factor) **9.88 /2022**
<http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357>

TOGETHER WE REACH THE GOAL
SJIF 2023: 5,971
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O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti administratsiyasi huzuridagi axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligida ro'yxatga olingan.

Ro'yxatga olish № 1189 Berilgan sanasi: 17-06-2021.

Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar jurnali Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar bazalariga kiritilgan.

Impact-faktor 2021 Evaluation Pending

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Jurnal jahon va mintaqaviy darajada fan va amaliyotning rivojlanish masalalariga bag'ishlangan.

Jurnal olimlar, o'qituvchilar, doktorantlar, talabalar uchun mo'ljallangan.

Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali.

2023. T.3. №2.

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

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«Al-Ferganus» LLC.
A. M. Abdullaev
“International journal of theoretical and practical research”
Scientific Journal.
Published since November 2021.
Schedule: monthly. 16+

Volume 3, Issue 2

February, 2023.

Chairman of the Editorial Board Salomov Uktam Rakhimovich, rector of FerPI

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Address of the editorial office:
150107
Fergana city, Fergana str., 86.
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alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

IF(Impact Factor) **9.88 / 2022**
<http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357>

TOGETHER WE REACH THE GOAL
SJIF 2023: 5,971
<http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994>

Registered with the Agency of Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
Registration No. 1189 dated 17-06-2021.

The journal "International Journal of Theoretical and Practical Research" is included Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar.

Impact-factor 2021 Evaluation Pending

License type supported CC: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

The Journal addresses issues of global and regional Science and Practice. For scientists, teachers, doctoral students, students.

(2022). International journal of theoretical and practical research, 3(2).

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«Al-Ferganus» ООО.

А. М. Абдуллаев

«Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований»

Научный журнал.

Издается с ноября 2021 г.

Выходит один раз в месяц. 16+

Том 3, Номер 2.

Февраль 2023 г.

Председатель редакционного совета Саломов Уктам Рахимович, ректор ФерПИ

Главный редактор К. И. Курпаяниди

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<https://alferganus.uz/en/site/index>

E-mail: alferganus.ltd@gmail.com

IF(Impact Factor) **9.88 /2022**

[http://journalseeker.research](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

[bib.com/view/issn/2181-](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

[2357](http://journalseeker.researchbib.com/view/issn/2181-2357)

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SJIF 2023:5,971

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[ort.php?id=21994](http://sjifactor.com/passport.php?id=21994)

Зарегистрирован в Агентстве информации и массовых коммуникаций при Администрации

Президента Республики Узбекистан.

Регистрации № 1189 от 17-06-2021.

Журнал «Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований» включен в Crossref, OpenAIRE, Google Scholar.

Импакт-факторы журнала: 2021 Evaluation Pending

Тип лицензии CC поддерживаемый журналом: Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0).

В журнале рассматриваются вопросы развития мировой и региональной науки и практики. Для ученых, преподавателей, докторантов, студентов.

Международный журнал теоретических и практических исследований. 2023. Т. 3. №2.

ISSN 2181-2357

9 772181 235007 >

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2023, Фергана, Узбекистан

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E'lon / Reklama / Advertisement

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QR CODE of this issue of the magazine <https://dx.doi.org/>

International journal of theoretical and practical research

Scientific Journal

Year: 2023 Issue: 2

Volume: 3

Published:

28.02.2023

<http://alferganus.uz>

Citation:

Xomidov, M. (2023). Analysis of the current state of innovation implementation in improving the competitiveness of industry. SJ International journal of theoretical and practical research, 3 (02), 56-64.

Xomidov, M. (2023). Analysis of the current state of innovation implementation in improving the competitiveness of industry. Nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar xalqaro jurnali, 3 (02), 56-64.

Doi:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7699555>

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UDC 338.242.2

ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF INNOVATION IMPLEMENTATION IN IMPROVING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF INDUSTRY

Abstract. *In this article, the importance of introducing innovations in the industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan and its role in the development of the economy, the way to the well-being of society today is highlighted. In addition, practical approaches to the level of bringing innovative processes to a new level were considered. How the innovative approaches of the digital economy at the international level are manifested in practice and the measures that should be implemented in this direction in our country have been studied.*

Key words: *Innovation, innovative activities, innovation, digital economics, digital economics, competitiveness ratings, dog industry.*

SANOAT RAQOBATDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHDA INNOVATSIYALARNI JORIY ETISHNING AHAMIYATI

Xomidov, Mirodiljon Xasanboy o'g'li

Farg'ona politexnika instituti, tayanch doktorant

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida innovatsiyalarni sanoatga joriy etishning ahamiyati va uni iqtisodiyotni rivojlanishidagi o'rni, bugungi kunda jamiyat farovonligi yo'li yoritilgan. Undan tashqari amaliy yondashuvlar innovatsion jarayonlarni yangi bosqichga olib chiqish darajasi ko'rib chiqilgan. Raqamli iqtisodiyotning xalqaro miqyosda innovatsion yondashuvlari amaliyota qay tarzda*

namoyon bo'lishi hamda mamlakatimizda ushbu yo'nalishda amalga oshirilishi lozim bo'lgan chora tadbirlari o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'lar: *innovatsiya, innovatsion faoliyat, innovatsiya ishlari, raqamli iqtisodiyot, raqamli iqtisod yo'nalishlari, raqobatbardoshlik reytinglari, IT sanoati.*

АНАЛИЗ СОВРЕМЕННОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ ИННОВАЦИЙ В ПОВЫШЕНИЕ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ

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Аннотация: *В данной статье освещается важность внедрения инноваций в промышленность Республики Узбекистан и ее роль в развитии экономики, пути к благополучию общества на сегодняшний день. Кроме того, были рассмотрены практические подходы к уровню вывода инновационных процессов на новый уровень. Изучено, как инновационные подходы цифровой экономики на международном уровне проявляются на практике и меры, которые следует реализовать в этом направлении в нашей стране.*

Ключевые слова: *инновации, инновационная деятельность, инновационная работа, цифровая экономика, направления цифровой экономики, рейтинги конкурентоспособности, ИТ-индустрия.*

Introduction

Currently, the new Uzbekistan is a rapidly developing country with a socially oriented market economy. The development strategy chosen by our government is aimed at the production of competitive, export-oriented and import-substituting products with high added value, based on the stable and proportionate growth of the industry and the modernization of production capacities, technical and technological updating. envisages the development of its leading sectors.

It is known from national and international experience that the level of development of the economy and society largely depends on innovative activities. For this reason, the introduction of the latest technologies in all aspects of our life is the main guarantee of development. Today, the introduction of innovations returns the following indicators (Fig. 1).

According to the State Statistics Committee, we can see that the rate of introduction of innovations in our country will return to growth by 2020. In particular, in 2018, 2,482 innovations were put into practice, and this number increased by 78% in 2019, and the number of technological innovations made this year was 4,011. Among them, the number of product innovations was 3017, and the number of process innovations was 994.

Fig. 1. The number of innovations introduced in the Republic of Uzbekistan ⁶

We can say that the main reason for this is the improvement of the legal framework of this industry in our country and the opening of a wide path for investments in the industry. According to the picture above, the innovative activity has slowed down a bit in the last 2 years. A decrease of 3.7% in 2020 and 1.9% in 2021 was observed. According to the analysis, the main reason for this is the emergence of the pandemic and the slowdown of the flow of capital in the international and national economy.

Literature analysis and methods

Researches on the introduction of innovations in industry are mainly focused on innovative systems, the laws of their implementation in local environments, and the application of public policy to innovation in networks, the presence of clusters or interregional innovation levels, and the influence of internal and external factors, and this process is based on classical innovation approaches. reflected.

However, the introduction of innovations is often considered a phenomenon that occurs at the level of firms. In this study, we analyzed the issue of innovative development at the macroeconomic level.

The main stage of development of innovative approaches at the macroeconomic level corresponded to the works of V. Zombart, V. Mitcherlich, Y. Schumpeter. The Austrian scientist Y. Schumpeter made a great contribution to the formation and development of innovations in industry. In addition, many other scientists, J. Friedman, who explained the theory of "growth points of regional industry" in his works, according to him, developing industrial points in the region are leaders in attracting capital and technology flow and achieve a high level of implementation. states that. F. Perru, "regional strategy" M. Porter, "competitive strategy" M. Porter, "economic

⁶ <https://www.stat.uz/uz/nashrlar/6436-o-zbekistonda-ilm-fan-va-innovatsion-faoliyat>

regionalization" N.N. Kolosovsky, "location of production" V. Launhardt, "long waves" N.D. Kondratiev, "territorial cluster M. Enright, "cumulative growth" G. Myrdal, "path dependence" P.A. David, "models of industrial districts" A. Marshall. In particular, based on N.D. Kondratiev's theory of long waves, the level of industrial development is directly related to changes in technological chains and polarization of technological processes. According to the scientist, technological chains are interconnected production groups.

Several foreign literatures showed a positive connection between the innovative development of the industry and export. He noted that the relationship between innovation and export in industry is relatively weak.

The regional distribution of the industrial sector is a process that depends not on the geography of research departments and human capital, but on the formation of the geography of industrial lands.

The general aspect of the theory of many scientists is that industrial firms are located in less dense areas due to the fact that industrial land is scattered and clearly defined according to geographical indicators. This is due to slow mobility of industrial entities, that is, the slowness of entering into market and capital flow relations, and geographical conditions have a negative impact on their innovative capacity. In addition to the studies of the above scientists, there are also some studies that cover these issues.

For example, Lapple et al. and Botha et al. have emphasized the role of regional knowledge spillovers in stimulating innovation processes in industry.

The purpose of this analytical article is to analyze the practice of introducing innovations and the causes of existing problems in the industry, which is the main link of the national economy as a complex socio-economic system.

In order to assess the state of the innovative potential of the national economy and eliminate the shortcomings in the implementation of high-tech projects, the following tasks are set:

- Study the experience of the world's leading countries in implementing innovation processes and improving them, and learn the aspects that match the potential of our country;
- to determine the current trends and prospective directions of digital transformation of the local economy, taking into account the specific features of the international experience of neo-industrial development.
- study and master the factors that contribute to the innovative development of the industry and the improvement of production in terms of quality and quantity

Factorial, historical, statistical, comparative and systematic methods of analysis, expert evaluation method were used in the research, which allowed the author to solve the tasks

Results

According to the results returned in 2021, the number of organizations that introduced technological innovations in our country was 1098, the highest share in the introduction of innovations by economic activity was observed in the manufacturing industry, and 669 organizations implemented innovations. According to the State Statistics Committee, the sectors with the highest share in the introduction of innovations are:

- Manufacturing industry - 44.2%
- Construction - 6.2%
- Agriculture, forestry and fisheries - 2.3%
- Information and communication - 4.2%
- Education - 1.2%
- Other activities - 40.2%

From the above information, it can be understood that the latest technologies are currently being introduced in production, which is the mainstay of the economy. We can see this in the table below.

It is no exaggeration to say that the main reason for this is the environment of pure competition and the fact that the field of production operates in direct connection with science. The reason why this sector has the lowest share can be attributed to the fact that there is little investment in this sector and that there are few highly qualified professionals.

Based on these data, it can be concluded that low-tech products have a large share in the manufacturing industry. Over the past two years, this industry has been leading the way. In this area, medium-low and medium-high-tech products occupy the next place, and the smallest share belongs to high-tech products.

Table 1.

The share of value added by the technological structure of the manufacturing industry
(in %)⁷

	2018	2019	2020	2021
Low-tech production	35,0	31,7	29,7	29,4
Medium-tech production (low level)	42,7	48,4	52,8	53,6
Medium-tech production (high level)	20,7	18,0	15,4	14,2
High-tech production	1,6	1,9	2,1	2,8

If we look at the technological indicators of the products created in the industry, in 2018, the share of high-tech production was 1.6%, and in the next 3 years, this number increased to 2.8%. In accordance with these figures, the volume of products produced on the basis of lower technological processes is decreasing from 35% to 29.9%.

Debate.

Innovations in production processes in our country and their implementation have a solid economic and legal foundation, but on the other hand, they do not correspond to the requirements, indicators and tasks of the development of the industrial revolution of the modern world to a certain extent.

Today, the funds spent on introducing innovations in the industrial sector in Uzbekistan are increasing year by year, of course, this is a good indicator, but almost 63%

⁷ <https://www.stat.uz/uz/matbuot-markazi/qo-mita-yangiliklar/23750-qaysi-yo-nalishdagi-korxonava-tashkilotlar-ko-proq-innovatsiyalami-joriy-etgan>

of the costs incurred for technological, marketing and organizational innovations are financed by the company's own funds. it's worth it. Creating innovations in this way increases production costs in the studio and, as a result, increases the cost of the product. And every enterprise with increased costs leads to a change in the level of profit remaining from goods and services. Information about this can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Expenditures on technological, marketing and organizational innovations by funding sources (in millions of soums)⁸

	2018	2019	2020	2021
own funds of the organization	2959428	3342925	4764543	15777060
foreign investment'	307078,5	1083650	605731,5	242753,4
commercial bank loans	501542,4	1060055	970973,2	806754,6
other funds	939162,6	1116844	488720,8	854221,2
Total	4707212	6603475	6829969	17680789

Over the past years, the country's development strategy has focused on innovation, and as a result, the flow of funds to this sector has increased dramatically. That's why many foreign companies prefer to follow the easy way of innovation. In particular, additional financial capitals are technologically developed at the expense of portfolio investments, attracting shares to the market or loans.

This process creates conditions for reducing the level of consumption from the situation that brought an excess load to the consumers in the market. The general background of this event leads to a change in the level of consumption in the country. Production in the general sense will not fail to react to this change.

In the above table, enterprises increased the indicator of spending their financial resources on investment processes by almost 5 times for 4 years. In particular, we can see that the loans of commercial banks allocated more funds by 60%. But the flow of financing from foreign investments and other sources decreased by 21% and 10.1%.

That's why many foreign companies prefer to follow the easy way of innovation. In particular, additional financial capitals are technologically developed at the expense of portfolio investments, attracting shares to the market or loans.

Conclusion

As a result of the research, the following conclusions can be drawn. The developed countries of the world are moving towards neo-industrial development based on modern principles, the main content of which is the cyber-physical digitization of production industries. Thus, the current trends and risks of the formation of a new technological

⁸ <https://www.stat.uz/uz/nashrlar/6436-o-zbekistonda-ilm-fan-va-innovatsion-faoliyat>

structure, neo-industrialization and the development of the socio-economic system are closely related to the delay in the modernization of production industries.

It has been confirmed that the innovative development of the industrial network is the main support point of the country's economic growth. In particular, a 1% increase in the annual growth rate of the industrial gross added value provides an opportunity to ensure an additional 1.02% increase in the annual growth rate of the republic's GDP. High-efficiency technologies are important in achieving this result. will play.

The main goals of the scientific and innovation policy of developed foreign countries are as follows: to increase the share of science and technology in the development of the country's economy; ensuring the progressive development of the material production sector; increase the competitiveness of national products in the world market; strengthening the country's defense capabilities; improvement of the ecological environment; maintaining and developing existing academic schools

Commercial enterprises in the market economy are legal and economic

liberalization and opening for them a corridor of effective cooperation with foreign enterprises is the main goal of our current innovation strategy.

As part of this research, the following scientific proposal and practical recommendations aimed at ensuring the ecological characteristics and efficiency of the production of industrial products were developed:

- development of software for structural and organizational issues in industry (web-based data processing)
- equipment for using digital technologies (feeding, maintenance, regulation of microclimate, milking, monitoring of animal condition and vital activity)
- promotion of industrial waste processing and activities of industries serving this industry;
 - establishing reasonable standards for the use of certain natural resources
 - cooperation with international organizations on digital technologies.
 - implementation of important projects on the introduction of digital technologies in organizations of all levels under the conditions of joint financing on the basis of state partnership.
- providing tax benefits to business entities that invest in innovative and manufacturing enterprises.
- to create a supporting infrastructure for the import of necessary technical technologies in terms of the introduction of digital technologies in business entities.

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№ 7430-3360-d0e2-4e5b-8cf1-9914-2923
Hujjat yaratilgan sana: 2021-06-22
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Hujjat berilgan: ОБЩЕСТВО С ОГРАНИЧЕННОЙ
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№ 1189

Nomi: "Xalqaro nazariy va amaliy tadqiqotlar"

Tarqatish shakli: jurnal

Til(lar)i: o'zbek, rus, ingliz

Muassis(lar)i: "AL-FERGANUS" mas'uliyati cheklangan jamiyat

Ixtisoslashuvi: fan sohalaridagi ilmiy nashr

Tahririyat manzili: 150100, Farg'ona viloyati, Farg'ona shahar, Mustaqillik ko'chasi, 42-uy

Tarqatish hududi: O'zbekiston Respublikasi hamda belgilangan tartibda chet davlatlarga

Berilgan sanasi: 17-06-2021

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